

The history of the formation of popular culture and its types: counterculture, subculture, popular culture, screen culture

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Abstract: A study of the topic of popular culture, showing its powerful influence in society and how it is connected to people's lives, attitudes and cultural values. How Popular Culture can be used in the teaching and learning of cultural concepts is embodied in this article.

Key words: culture, counterculture, thinking, consciousness, subculture

Enter. Popular culture is a unique form of culture that is complex and not always interpreted in the same way. It is common to understand popular culture as a phenomenon related to Western culture, as well as to evaluate it as an example of lack of ideas, quality and taste. At the same time, folklore and folk culture are interpreted as manifestations of mass culture. Popular culture has deep social and cultural roots. The socio-economic roots of the emergence of mass culture are connected with the emergence of large-scale industrial production. If the development of large-scale industry created a need for hired workers, the collapse of the traditional social structure of the feudal society created a mass of people who lost their usual work and served to satisfy this need. The formation of mass culture was a reflection of this process. After all, it was formed as a result of the aspiration of new social strata (hired workers and servants) to create their own culture. The emergence and development of popular culture is also the transfer of social values to a simple, understandable language, the growth of mass literacy, and the emergence of publishing products. For a long time, worldviews and norms of behavior were passed down from the teacher to the students individually. Historical development, social experience and the universalization of the transmission mechanism have brought them to a wider range. This should also be considered as an important aspect of mass culture formation. Today, we can see the unique result of this process in kindergartens, schools, and higher educational

institutions, when the educational process is organized on the basis of a universalized model and programs. Such universalization is now gaining a global scale.

In the 20th century, as a result of the emergence of radio, cinema, TV, video, computer systems, a new stage of the development of mass culture was entered. This stage is characterized by a sharp increase in the possibilities of forming views and values acceptable to the majority. With the help of means such as advertising and fashion, which have become subtle and powerful tools of influence, it is an attempt to form a physically fit person by actively promoting various types of sports that serve to be physically healthy at a time when intellectual activity is increasingly pushing out physical labor from all areas. is the result of the process. Mass culture, unlike folk culture, can acquire not only a national, but also an international, international character, and at the same time, it can be far from national. In most cases, the national affiliation of a particular sample of mass culture can be distinguished only by its language or performer. Elite culture was distinguished by the fact that it was not intended for the masses and was incomprehensible, which served to give its carriers a special position in society. Popular culture is distinguished by its specific authors who are popular among the general public. Folk culture has always been associated with a certain place. In popular culture, such locality is not observed. It will be aimed at a wide audience from the start. It is based on human emotions - love, fear, desire to achieve success, faith in the strangeness, and so on. In this way, mass culture creates a landscape of life that is similar to real life in some respects, but at the same time somewhat distant from it, serves to form a system of views and values, a model of behavior. With these features, popular culture strives to satisfy the natural need of a person for an ideal.

Popular culture is interpreted differently by scientists and experts. They can be summed up as follows: 1. Popular culture is a concept that represents people's culture, traditions, rituals, art, etc. 2. Popular culture is a phenomenon related to the development of mass media. 3. Mass production, a negative phenomenon in the

form of mass-produced examples of culture created by the "entertainment industry". Today, mass culture has become one of the most dangerous weapons of cultural and ideological oppression. Mass culture, which is the core of consumerism, is a phenomenon that contradicts the original culture of the individual, violates it, destroys its essence, and ultimately lowers a person to the level of a living being, an animal, and turns the people into a crowd. Today, mass media and TV serve as the main means and source of popularization of culture. This is manifested, first of all, in the transformation of any problem that expresses people's sadness and happiness, into a commodity, into a stereotyped entertainment. Fundamental changes in the value system under the influence of the processes of globalization and the expansion of mass culture, which is one of its directions, cause certain changes in the person who is considered a "social being", the person and society are deprived of their spiritual and moral support, and the society is in crisis.

A subculture is a set of values and routines of a group of people who are united by a particular worldview, united by specific interests that define their worldview. Subculture is a sovereign entity, a part of public culture.

From the point of view of cultural studies, subcultures are associations of people that do not contradict the values of traditional culture, but complement it.

A subculture may differ from the dominant culture in language, behavior, clothing, etc. The basis of subculture can be music style, lifestyle, certain political views. Some subcultures are extreme in nature and protest against society or certain social events. Some subcultures are closed in nature and tend to isolate their members from society. Sometimes subcultures develop and enter as an element of a single culture of society. Developed subcultures have their own periodicals, clubs, public organizations.

A narrower concept that is close to subculture, but does not replace it, is fandom (English fandom - fanaticism) - as a rule, a group of fans of a certain topic (writer, performer, style). A fandom may share some cultural characteristics, such as party jokes and slang, similar interests outside of the fandom, and its own

publications and websites. However, most fandoms do not form subcultures, they focus only on the topic of their interest. Also, the concept of a hobby is sometimes confused with the concept of a subculture, a person's passion for any profession (gamers, hackers, etc.). Communities of people with common hobbies can form a stable fandom, but at the same time do not have the signs of a subculture (common image, worldview, common taste in many areas).

Today's interactive television technology includes many set-top boxes, some of which include hard drives, which allow viewers to change, pause, and record screen clips while watching television programs. can be removed. Interactive communication in television art is carried out in the selection of art programs by telephone, in asking the public opinion about a particular art program, in the daily correction of contemporary culture more.

Let's briefly touch on the acceptability of the concept of "computer art". Using the capabilities of a modern screen through the Internet, the user has the opportunity to choose a wide range of artistic values, and also has the opportunity to participate in the creation of artistic works. Although the creation of such works does not allow us to talk about art in the absence of professional education, it is impossible to emphasize the unquestionable influence of modern computer technologies on art in the following areas:

On the one hand, computer screen technology is used in the creative works of artists and sculptors, painters and composers; on the other hand, modern mass media present high culture to the public and thereby diminish its value.

Thus, for example, most of the attempts to use computer technology in art are related to painting and drawing, which gives rise to two approaches to the use of computers in this field, in the first case, the computer plays a role. a simple tool, in the second, the artist installs a program for the machine, does not know what will come from it, and the computer itself creates a work of art that can only be conventionally called such.

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